

CASE STUDY: MURCIA

This policy brief is an outcome of the NEVERMORE project. It was developed through a multi-step process that combined the characterization of the Murcia region, the definition of key policy storylines, expert consultations, and stakeholder surveys on implementation barriers and enablers. The effect of selected policies on key indicators was simulated using System Dynamics modelling, with an implementation period from 2030 to 2045 and two climate change scenarios (SSP2-4.5, an intermediate greenhouse gas emissions scenario, and SSP5-8.5, a very high greenhouse gas emissions scenario). Results from model simulations and the insights gathered throughout the process are the basis for the technical and policy recommendations presented in this brief.

Key Messages

Murcia's climate makes it highly vulnerable to droughts and floods, threatening agriculture, tourism and water security. Climate action should combine risk-reduction measures with improved cropland management, an integrated water policy expanding supply options while cutting demand, and mitigation measures for decarbonization and self-sufficiency. Implementation needs institutional support and better guidance to access available funds and to overcome high costs and skills gaps.

The Region of Murcia is an autonomous community of Spain located in the southeast of the Iberian Peninsula, on the coast of the Mediterranean Sea.

The climate is defined as semi-arid subtropical Mediterranean, characterized by high temperatures and scarce and irregular rainfall.

Murcia has faced multiple natural disasters over the past decade, including severe floods and prolonged droughts.

Main economic sectors, challenges, and priorities

Agriculture: The most relevant economic sector in Murcia is agriculture. Favorable climatic and territorial conditions allow a great variety and volume of crop production, but Murcia's agriculture faces a range of risks that threaten its sustainability and productivity. Among these, droughts and hydrogeological risks, particularly flooding, play a significant role, directly impacting crops, agricultural infrastructure, and soil quality.

Water: Considering the semi-arid climate conditions, water is a key resource. Water exploitation from the primary sector and scarce rainfall challenge water security. Further, Murcia has experienced severe drought conditions over the past decade, exacerbated by climate change. These droughts have led to critical water shortages, affecting agriculture, ecosystems, and drinking water availability.

Tourism: Another important economic activity is tourism, which is also affected by climate-related hazards (high temperature and floods) and water scarcity.

Priorities: All these aspects underscore the importance of sustainable water management and climate adaptation strategies in the region. Indeed, Murcia's main priorities are to combat the loss of productive land and ensure water security, while also promoting a low-carbon economy.

Decision-making and implementation context

Murcia's climate action is shaped by EU and national frameworks, implemented by the regional government and delivered locally by municipalities. Municipalities translate regional priorities into local plans, while the region coordinates strategy, standards, and support. Stronger coordination is needed to align funding, data, and project pipelines across levels of government.

1. Increase the capacity to adapt

Substantial economic losses due to floods in urban areas can be prevented by implementing flood defences, with an 18% reduction compared to the baseline. At the same time, the adaptive capacity of Murcia's population can be increased by providing education and training, while sensitivity can be minimized by improving green urban planning. A high implementation of such policies, supported by substantial incentives for education and training, can reduce climate-related risks for Murcia's population to zero, even under the most adverse future climate scenario. The greatest benefits can be achieved by providing education and training to at least 50% of the population and by implementing green urban areas covering at least 30 km² in the region. Considering that insufficient and complex funding mechanisms may constrain the implementation of extensive adaptation policies, guidance for navigating funding opportunities should be provided, ensuring that opportunities (e.g., programmes and initiatives linked to European Structural and Investment Funds - ESIF) are effectively accessed.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Flood defences in urban areas	yes	yes	yes
Green urban planning (km ²)	10	30	50
Education and training (% of population)	20	50	80

Risk index for Murcia's population (0-1). It is calculated accounting for the probability of heatwaves, the exposed population, and their sensitivity and adaptive capacity. Dmnl= dimensionless.

2. Protect agricultural production through improved cropland and water management

Murcia's agricultural production can be preserved by diversifying production, increasing water availability and use efficiency, and investing in crop adaptation. Increasing water storage on agricultural land is key to addressing water scarcity in the municipality, though this would reduce the available area for crop production.

Crop diversification and increased water availability can reduce crop sensitivity to climate hazards, with the best results obtained with a high level of policy implementation, i.e., more than 50% of crop diversification and increased water use efficiency.

At the same time, substantial incentives are needed to promote crops' adaptive capacity, representing the main driver for improved cropland management, together with simplified bureaucratic procedures.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Investments in crop adaptation (million €)	10	50	100
Crop diversification (% of cropland)	20	50	80
Efficient water demand from agriculture (% reduction)	20	50	80
Water storage increase (Hm ³)	10	50	100

Risk index for crops in Murcia (0-1). It is calculated accounting for the drought exceedance probability, the ratio of exposed crops, as well as crops sensitivity and adaptive capacity. Dmnl=dimensionless

3. Sustainable use of water resources

Water scarcity in Murcia can be contrasted with a comprehensive, integrated water policy aimed at increasing water availability and reducing water demand across sectors. Ambitious water policies to reduce water demand from the agricultural, industrial, and urban sectors by 80% and increase water storage and supply by more than 300 Hm³ through desalination, transboundary water, and wastewater treatment can ensure water security under different climate scenarios.

This would allow increasing the percentage of irrigated cropland, although a high implementation of water storage and afforestation policies would lead to a decline in total agricultural land. The integration of sectoral and water management policies is crucial to address cross-sectoral challenges and avoid trade-offs, which requires policy coherence and multi-stakeholder engagement. While financial support is a key driver, barriers such as a lack of knowledge and skills, high investment costs, and insufficient institutional support should be addressed for successful implementation.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Efficient water demand from agriculture, industry and urban areas (% reduction in demand)	20	50	80
Water storage increase (Hm ³)	10	50	100
Desalination increase (Hm ³)	10	50	100
Water treatment increase (Hm ³)	10	50	100
Transboundary water conditions (Hm ³)	20	27	70

Water security is represented by a binary index equal to 0 when the water supply is insufficient to meet demand and equal to 1 when the supply fully satisfies demand. Dmnl=dimensionless

4. A resilient and diversified tourism sector

Tourism in Murcia can increase its capacity to cope with climate-related hazards, while also increasing its sustainability, by deseasonalizing tourist flows and investing in infrastructure. The risk index for tourism increases with the exposure to climate hazards; spreading tourist flows throughout the year and investing in adaptation and resilience not only can reduce risks but also increase revenues. Policies that promote resilient infrastructure with sustained investments can counteract the decline in tourist capacity, while a sustainable use of water resources from urban areas should be prioritised to reduce the increasing water demand.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Promote domestic tourism (% increase of national tourists)	20	50	80
Promote all year tourism (% of seasonal spread)	20	50	80
Investment in touristic infrastructure (% increase)	20	50	80

a) Risk index for tourism (0-1) and b) tourism income in Murcia for baseline and policy scenarios. Dmnl=dimensionless

5. A more efficient use of energy for climate change mitigation and adaptation

Climate change adaptation and mitigation go hand in hand, so that improving resource use efficiency can both increase resilience and reduce emissions. Increasing energy efficiency by 30% can substantially reduce energy consumption in Murcia, supporting a transformative transition to renewables. Such policies would enable drastic reductions in CO2 emissions from the energy sector, with zero emissions in the high implementation scenario. At the same time, a lower demand for energy and phasing out oil and gas as an energy sources would be

beneficial in terms of self-sufficiency and resilience, which is crucial in times of high instability.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Energy efficiency (% increase)	10	20	30
Energy transition model	Gradual	Good	Best
Incentives for energy efficiency and lower emissions	Low	Medium	High

Total energy consumption (MWh) in Murcia under two climate scenarios (SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5) for baseline and policy scenarios.

6. A pathway to decarbonization

Although climate change adaptation is often prioritized at the local level, mitigation actions are nonetheless urgent. A switch to clean energy, increasing solar (including rooftop installations) and hydrogen capacity while reducing non-renewables, would contribute to a low-carbon future and increase total energy production in Murcia. Indeed, a robust implementation of renewable energy policies, with an increase in total solar capacity to 300 MW, would mitigate the decline in energy production in the region. This would reduce the need for energy imports, especially if hydrogen is not included in the energy mix. An ambitious energy policy would be in line with ESIF programmes that allocate resources to projects for renewable energy production, sustainable mobility, and green infrastructure.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Solar capacity increase (MWh)	50	100	200
Solar production on rooftops increase (MWh)	10	50	100
Reduction in non-renewables production (MWh)	100	250	500
Incentives for renewables and carbon tax	Low	Medium	High

Total energy production (MWh) in Murcia under baseline and policy scenarios.

Conclusions:

Murcia's main challenges can be addressed through integrated water management, flood protection, and land-use/ecosystem measures. Model simulations suggest that education and training, along with the implementation of flood defences and green urban areas, can reduce economic losses and drive the population risk index to (near) zero, reinforcing the role of social and urban measures in risk reduction. Water security remains a binding constraint for agricultural production, underscoring the need for coordinated water demand management, storage, and diversified supply. Increasing energy efficiency and shifting to renewables can reduce the need for energy imports while lowering emissions.

CATALOGUE & LOCAL TOOL

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